

EDEN ISS

D 7.4 – Newsletter 4

prepared for

WP 7.1 - Public Engagement

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1.0	30.4.2019	Barbara Imhof	Initial Release

Executive summary

The Newsletter (D7.4) is part of WP7.1 Public Engagement of the EDEN ISS project. As part of the official closing of the EDEN ISS project the Newsletter was issued to approximately 1600 people through MailChimp and distributed to the EDEN ISS portal which has a reach of a couple of thousand viewers per day.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
Acronyms	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project	6
1.2 Purpose and scope of this document.....	6
2 Newsletter 4	7
2.1 Online Access.....	7
3 Summary	8
4 Press Release	9

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
AIAA	American Institute of Aeronautics	IP	Intellectual Property
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
AST	Airbus Defence and Space	ISS	International Space Station
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	ISLWG	Information Systems Liaison Working Group
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
CEA	Controlled Environment Agriculture	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
CNR	National Research Council	LSG	LIQUIFER Systems Group
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research	M#	Month Number
D	Deliverable	PP	Program Participants
DLO	Wageningen University and Research	RD	Reference Document
DLR	German Aerospace Center	R&D	Research & Development
DLR-RY	German Aerospace Center - Institute of Space Systems	SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
EC	European Commission	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
EDEN	Evolution and Design of Environmentally-Closed Nutrition-Sources	TBD	To Be Determined
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency	UoG	University of Guelph
EU	European Union	WP	Work Package
HS	Heliospectra AB		
IAC	International Astronautical Congress		

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project

The objective is to inform the public and interested stakeholders through global distribution

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

Summary of the Newsletter 4.

2 Newsletter 4

2.1 *Online Access*

The Newsletter can be retrieved online permanently via MailChimp

<https://mailchi.mp/bdbe2707326a/eden-iss-greenhouse-remains-in-antarctica>

and on the EDEN ISS website via

<https://eden-iss.net/index.php/2019/04/30/eden-iss-mobile-test-facility-remains-in-antarctica/>

3 Summary

This Newsletter concludes the project and highlights the extension of the EDEN ISS project and the facility for another 2 years until 2021. It was published on 30 April 2019 via MailChimp and on the EDEN ISS website.

4 Press Release

Press Release - April 2019

EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility remains in Antarctica!

The first *EDEN ISS Antarctic mission (February – November 2018) aimed at advancing controlled environment agriculture technologies for plant cultivation in extreme conditions*, applicable to both terrestrial earth and space exploration. In April 2019, the EU-funded project comes to a complete close with all research concluded, providing definitive results. Due to the advantages this **unique learning platform** offers, it has been decided to **extend research missions into 2021**.

Partner institutions German Aerospace Center (DLR) and Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), operators of the German Antarctic research center Neumayer Station III, will keep the analogue facility in operation for a minimum of two years until 2021, enabling two more isolation phases. Between January and February 2019, the facility was updated with repairs made to all subsystems where required. A complete cleaning of the greenhouse was performed preparing the facility for future research and analogue testing.

Researchers interested in taking advantage of the highly isolated conditions of Antarctica, remote monitoring and communication system, and/or the high-functioning systems architecture of the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility are invited to contact Dr. Daniel Schubert to submit research proposals.

In April 2019, the EU-funded project comes to a close with first phase research concluded, providing definitive results.

During the Antarctic mission, a significant amount of fruits and vegetables were produced in the Future Exploration Greenhouse and were a great benefit to the over-wintering crew at the Neumayer Station III. A large amount of plant and microbiological samples from within the greenhouse have been preserved and are currently being tested by project partners for determining further the quality and safety of the cultivated fruits and vegetables.

photo credit DLR, 2018

The EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility is comprised of two standard shipping containers fitted-out to accommodate a Future Exploration Greenhouse, a service section, a climatic buffer zone, and all the required subsystems for operating a controlled-environment greenhouse (including an LED Illumination System, Atmosphere Management System & Thermal Control System, a Nutrient Delivery System, and Plant Health Monitoring system, and an all-in-one hardware and software platform for monitoring and controlling all equipment and for communications between the Mission Control Centre in Bremen.)

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photo credit DLR, 2018

The EDEN ISS project was a collaboration among 14 international partners from 8 countries worldwide demonstrating safe food production technologies and operational procedures under representative conditions. EDEN ISS was funded by Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, Grant agreement no. 636501.

Germany

DLR German Aerospace Center, Germany
Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
Airbus Defence and Space, Germany

Austria

LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria

Italy

National Research Council, Italy
Enginsoft S.p.A., Italy
Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A., Italy
Arescosmo S.p.A., Italy
Telespazio S.p.A., Italy

Netherlands

Wageningen University and Research, the Netherlands

Sweden

Heliospectra AB, Sweden

Ireland

Limerick Institute of Technology, Ireland

Canada

University of Guelph, Canada

USA

University of Florida, US

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